

1 **Ccdc141 is regulated developmentally while Ccdc47 expression characterizes the embryonic state**
2 **in iPS and TE.**

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8 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
9 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here Ccdc gene family
10 interplay during lineage commitment in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo involving Ccdc141 and
11 Ccdc47.

12 Citations

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